

Dirhenium paddlewheel complexes bearing *para*-substituted triphenylguanidinate ligands : Synthesis, spectroscopic and computational studies[†]

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Abstract : The quadruply bonded dirhenium(III) complexes, $[\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-TPG}^{\text{R}})_4\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$, bridged by four *para*-substituted triphenylguanidinate ligands (TPG^R, R = H, Me, OMe) have been synthesized by the reaction of molten HTPG^R and $[\text{Bu}_4\text{N}]_2\text{Re}_2\text{Cl}_8$ (Bu = n-butyl). Conductivity measurements of the complexes in acetone solution confirmed their electrolytic nature. These complexes have very similar spectral and electrochemical properties, which are also reported. The identities of the complexes have been established by ESI-mass spectrometry. The electronic structures of the complexes are also scrutinized by density functional theory (DFT) calculations.

Keywords : Dirhenium, synthesis, triphenylguanidine, density functional theory, mass spectrometry, melt reaction.

Introduction

Metal-metal bonded dirhenium complexes are of interest because of their rich redox properties¹. The Re_2^{n+} core can adopt a large number of stable oxidation states ranging from Re_2^{4+} to Re_2^{8+} ^{1,2}. The quadruply bonded dirhenium(III) compound $[\text{Bu}_4\text{N}]_2\text{Re}_2\text{Cl}_8$, **1** (Bu = n-butyl) with $\sigma^2\pi^4\delta^2$ electronic configuration has been prepared almost four decades ago³. Since then efforts have been made to develop the reaction chemistry of this useful synthon **1**. Because of the presence of δ -bond, **1** possesses an eclipsed configuration with a D_{4h} symmetry. The substitutional lability of the Cl ligands in **1** has been demonstrated by its reaction with an excess of thiocyanate or selenocyanate ligand in non-aqueous medium which produces $[\text{Bu}_4\text{N}]_2[\text{Re}_2(\text{NCS})_8]$ and $[\text{Bu}_4\text{N}]_2[\text{Re}_2(\text{NCSe})_8]$ respectively⁴. The first trifluoroacetate complex of dirhenium(III), $(\text{Bu}_4\text{N})\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-O}_2\text{CCF}_3)\text{Cl}_6$, was obtained by the solvothermal reaction of **1** with $\text{CF}_3\text{COOH}/(\text{CF}_3\text{CO})_2\text{O}$ mixture⁵. The dirhenium tetracarboxylate derivatives, $\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-O}_2\text{CR})_4\text{Cl}_2$, have also been prepared from **1**⁶. The reaction of **1** with *N,N'*-diphenylformamidinate ligand has also been well documented in the literature⁷. Dirhenium complexes containing bis(diphenylphosphino)methane (dppm) ligand, *cis*- $\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-O}_2\text{CCH}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2(\mu\text{-dppm})_2$ and $\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-O}_2\text{CCH}_3)\text{Cl}_4(\mu\text{-dppm})_2$

have also been synthesized by reacting **1** with varying amount of dppm and acetic acid/acetic anhydride mixture in alcohol medium⁸. The triply bonded dirhenium(II) compound, $\text{Re}_2\text{Cl}_4(\mu\text{-dppm})_2$, has also been prepared by reacting **1** with dppm and sodium acetate in refluxing ethanol⁹.

Because of the strong electron-donating ability of the guanidinate ligands, they have attracted much attention in coordination chemistry. Guanidinate ligands have frequently been used to stabilize mononuclear¹⁰ as well as dimetallic units¹¹. They can bind the metal center in the mono-ion, di-ion or neutral forms¹². The guanidinate mono anion can also delocalize its uncoordinated nitrogen lone pair into its π -system (Scheme 1). This delocalization would result in an enhancement of the basicity of the

Scheme 1

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

ligand and its ability to stabilize the higher oxidation states of the metal¹³. Of the diverse array of dirhenium complexes that are known, few have been isolated that contain guanidinate ligand in the coordination sphere. The compounds that we are aware of are the dirhenium paddlewheel compounds $\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-hpp})_4\text{Cl}_2$, $\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-hpp})_3\text{Cl}_3$ and $[\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-hpp})_4\text{Cl}_2]^+$ where hpp = 1,3,4,6,7,8-hexahydro-2H-pyrimido[1,2-a]pyrimidine^{2a,14}. The unprecedented highly oxidized Re_2^{8+} species with the hpp ligand was also isolated and spectroscopically characterized^{2b}. We have recently reported a mixed μ -acetato/ μ -guanidinato dirhenium complex, $[\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-TPG})_3(\mu\text{-O}_2\text{CCH}_3)\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$, **2** with the 1,2,3-triphenylguanidine (HTPG) ligand¹⁵. The HTPG ligand was chosen because of its exceptional capacity to stabilize the metal-metal multiply bonded compounds in higher oxidation states¹³. By varying the organic substituent on HTPG, it is also possible to tune the steric and electronic properties of the ligand¹⁶.

Aiming at the extension of these studies and further exploration of the reactivity of dirhenium center towards HTPG ligand, we examine the reaction of **1** with different *para*-substituted triphenylguanidine ligands (HTPG^R, Chart 1). In the course of this work we have discovered that HTPG^R reacts with **1** in the solid state at 165 °C to afford the dirhenium paddlewheel complexes with the formula $[\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-TPG}^{\text{R}})_4\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$, **3(R)**. The synthetic procedures and properties of the resulting complexes are reported. To get better insight into the geometry and electronic structure of these complexes, density functional theory (DFT) studies have also been included.

Chart 1

Experimental

Materials :

The compound $[\text{Bu}_4\text{N}]_2\text{Re}_2\text{Cl}_8$, **1** was prepared by the literature method³. 1,2,3-Triphenylguanidine (HTPG^H) was purchased from TCI-India and other substituted guanidines (HTPG^{Me}, HTPG^{OMe}) were prepared by a literature method¹⁷. All other reagents were obtained from commercial sources and were used as received, except for drying of solvents by routine techniques. All manipulations were carried out under an inert atmosphere using Schlenk techniques.

Synthesis of complexes :

Synthesis of $[\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-TPG}^{\text{H}})_4\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$, **3(H) :** A Schlenk flask was charged with $[\text{Bu}_4\text{N}]_2\text{Re}_2\text{Cl}_8$ (100 mg, 0.087 mmol), HTPG^H (200 mg, 0.696 mmol) and a small stir bar. The mixture was heated at 165 °C overnight while stirring; it afforded a dark green residue. After the residue cooled to room temperature, it was washed with diethyl ether (6 × 10 ml) to remove the excess ligand. The dark green powder thus obtained was dried *in vacuo*. Recrystallization of this green residue from dichloromethane resulted in green microcrystalline solid. Yield : 68%; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{76}\text{H}_{64}\text{N}_{12}\text{Cl}_2\text{Re}_2$: C, 57.46; H, 4.06; N, 10.58. Found : C, 57.41; H, 4.11; N, 10.51%; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ) : 6.04 (d, arom, *J* 8 Hz), 6.73–7.47 (m, arom); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3376 [ν_{NH}], 1593 [$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$]; UV/Vis (CH_2Cl_2) λ_{max} (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$) : 443 (12740), 577 (1720); $E_{1/2}$ (vs Ag/AgCl, CH_2Cl_2 , scan rate 100 mV s^{-1}) : 0.21 V ($\Delta E_{\text{p}} = 340$ mV); MS (ESI+, CH_3CN) : (m/z) $\{\text{M-Cl}\}^+$ Calcd : 1553.4180, Found : 1553.4093.

Synthesis of $[\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-TPG}^{\text{Me}})_4\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$, **3(Me) :** This complex was prepared by the same procedure as that for **3(H)** with $[\text{Bu}_4\text{N}]_2\text{Re}_2\text{Cl}_8$ (100 mg, 0.087 mmol) and HTPG^{Me} (230 mg, 0.696 mmol). Yield : 63%; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{88}\text{H}_{88}\text{N}_{12}\text{Cl}_2\text{Re}_2$: C, 60.16; H, 5.05; N, 9.57. Found : C, 60.20; H, 5.11; N, 9.54%; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ) : 2.24 (s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 6.05 (d, arom, *J* 8 Hz), 6.59–7.47 (m, arom); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3376 [ν_{NH}], 1593 [$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$]; UV/Vis (CH_2Cl_2) λ_{max} (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$) : 444 (15530), 577 (2090); $E_{1/2}$ (vs Ag/AgCl, CH_2Cl_2 , scan rate 100 mV s^{-1}) : 0.23 V ($\Delta E_{\text{p}} = 320$ mV); MS (ESI+, CH_3CN) : (m/z) $\{\text{M-Cl}\}^+$ Calcd : 1721.6058, Found : 1721.6028.

Synthesis of $[Re_2(\mu\text{-TPG}^{OMe})_4Cl]Cl$, **3(OMe) :** The procedure was the same as that for **3(H)** with HTPG^{OMe} (263 mg, 0.696 mmol). Yield : 65%; Anal. Calcd. for C₈₈H₈₈N₁₂O₁₂Cl₂Re₂ : C, 54.23; H, 4.55; N, 8.62. Found : C, 54.29; H, 4.57; N, 8.56%; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, δ) : 3.74 (s, -OCH₃), 6.04 (d, arom, *J* 8 Hz), 6.63–7.46 (m, arom); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3376 [*v*_{NH}], 1593 [*v*_{C=N}]; UV/Vis (CH₂Cl₂) λ_{max} (ε, M⁻¹ cm⁻¹) : 444 (16230), 577 (2190); *E*_{1/2} (vs Ag/AgCl, CH₂Cl₂, scan rate 100 mV s⁻¹) : 0.21 V (Δ*E*_p = 330 mV); MS (ESI+, CH₃CN) : (*m/z*) {M-Cl}⁺ Calcd : 1913.5448, Found : 1913.5325.

Physical measurements :

Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer L120-00A FT-IR spectrometer as a KBr pellet. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-1800 PC spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra were collected on a Bruker DPX-400 spectrometers in CDCl₃. Microanalyses were performed using a Perkin-Elmer 2400 series-II elemental analyser. Conductivity measurements were performed on a Systronics 304 digital conductivity meter. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded with a CHI 600D series instrument with a Pt working electrode, a Pt wire auxiliary electrode, and a Ag/AgCl reference electrode in dichloromethane solution with tetrabutylammonium perchlorate as the supporting electrolyte. Electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (ESI-MS) data were obtained using an Agilent-6538 Ultra high definition (UHD) accurate Mass-Q-TOF (LC-HRMS) instrument.

Computational study :

Unrestricted Kohn-Sham geometry optimizations were performed for **3(H)**, **3(Me)** and **3(OMe)** and single-point calculation on the optimized geometry was performed for **3(H)** with the ORCA 2.9.1 electronic structure package¹⁸. The geometries of the complexes were fully optimized in the gas phase without any symmetry constraints. Geometry optimizations for the complexes were converged to the *S* = 0 spin and employed the Becke-Perdew (BP86) functional¹⁹ and the SV(P) (Ahlich splitvalence polarized) basis set with the SV/C auxiliary basis set for all atoms except for nitrogen and chlorine, for which the larger TZVP (Ahlich triple-valence polarized) basis set in conjunction with the TZV/J auxiliary basis set was

used²⁰. For rhenium atoms, the scaled zeroth-order regular approximation (ZORA) Hamiltonian was used to account for relativistic effects in the calculations²¹. These calculations employed the resolution of identity (RI) approximation developed by Neese²². Single-point calculation was optimized with a Grid4 optimization grid and tight self-consistent field (SCF) convergence criteria. This calculation employed the B3LYP functional²³ and ZORA (Re), TZVP (N and Cl), and SVP (C and H) basis sets. Isosurface plots of molecular orbitals were generated with the gOpenMol program by using isodensity value of 0.04.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

The melt reactions of the dirhenium(III) synthon, [Bu₄N]₂Re₂Cl₈, with three different *para*-substituted triphenylguanidine ligands (HTPG^R, R = H, Me, OMe) at 165 °C overnight afford products in which the seven chlorido ligands are displaced. The resulting complexes contain four bridging triphenylguanidinate ligands. The complexes were isolated as dark green microcrystalline

solids in good yields. The specific compounds are identified by the R group in parentheses, for example, **3(Me)** represents [Re₂(μ-TPG^{Me})₄Cl]Cl. The molecular structures of the complexes of type **3(R)** have been authenticated by different analytical techniques and density functional theory calculation. The complexes are diamagnetic, in agreement with the dimetallic oxidation state +6 (σ²π⁴δ²). They are soluble in a variety of organic solvents, such as dichloromethane, acetone, acetonitrile, tetrahydrofuran *etc.* The 1 : 1 electrolytic nature of the complexes have been confirmed by conductivity measurements in acetone solution (Λ_M = 102 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ for **3(H)**; 110 for **3(Me)** and 114 for **3(OMe)**). The complexes of type **3(R)** have very similar spectroscopic and cyclic voltammetric properties (*vide infra*) which implies that there is a close similarity between their electronic and molecular structures.

Spectroscopic and electrochemical studies :

The optical absorption spectra of the complexes in

dichloromethane solution were recorded at room temperature and display well-resolved peaks in the region 300–700 nm (Fig. 1). All three complexes show a medium intensity broad peak at ~ 580 nm and an intense sharp peak at ~ 440 nm. In the IR spectra of the complexes,

Fig. 1. Electronic absorption spectra of **3(R)** in dichloromethane solution.

two clearly separated set of bands are observed, one with wave number above 2880 cm^{-1} and the other below 1595 cm^{-1} . The medium intensity band at $\sim 3317\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was assigned to the N–H stretching vibration. The C=N stretching mode was observed at $\sim 1594\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The C–H stretching modes are visible between 2888 and 3058 cm^{-1} . The C–N stretching modes, phenyl ring C–C stretching modes and some of the C–H bending modes appear between 1528 and 1303 cm^{-1} . The C–H in-plane bending modes were detected in the region 1259 – 1014 cm^{-1} , and the out-of-plane bending modes²⁴ were observed at 690 and 758 cm^{-1} .

The NMR spectra obtained for the complexes are consistent with their formulation. In the ^1H NMR spectra of **3(R)** in CDCl_3 , the aromatic hydrogens of the phenyl rings of the four TPG^R ligands were located as a multiplet in the region 6.03–7.52 ppm. The N–H protons are very much broadened and could not be seen.

All the complexes of type **3(R)** are electroactive in dichloromethane solution and display one quasi-reversible one-electron cyclic voltammetric response, which is assignable to the $\text{Re}_2^{7+}/\text{Re}_2^{6+}$ couple and corresponds to the configuration change $\sigma^2\pi^4\delta^2 \rightarrow \sigma^2\pi^4\delta^1$. The voltammograms are shown in Fig. 2. The complexes have wave centered at $E_{1/2}$ of $\sim 0.20\text{ V}$ (vs Ag/AgCl) which clearly indicates that this wave corresponds to a first oxi-

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of **3(R)** in dichloromethane solution recorded at a scan rate of 100 mV s^{-1} .

dation to $[\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-TPG}^{\text{R}})_4\text{Cl}]^{2+}$ complex with a Re_2^{7+} core. Since the $E_{1/2}$ of ferrocene/ferrocenium couple is 0.44 V under similar conditions, efforts are being made to oxidize the **3(R)** complexes by ferrocenium hexafluorophosphate $[(\text{FcCp}_2)\text{PF}_6]$ and to isolate the oxidized species in stable form.

We have not been able to prepare crystals of complexes **3(R)** suitable for X-ray diffraction experiments. Accordingly, we used ESI-MS to aid in defining the molecular composition of **3(R)**. The acetonitrile solutions of the complexes were positive-ion electro sprayed into a quadrupole ion-trap mass spectrometer and subjected to collision-induced dissociation to gain the structural informations. The ESI-MS spectrum of **3(H)** exhibits a prominent ion peak at $m/z = 1553.4093$, whose mass and isotope pattern corresponds to the $[\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-TPG}^{\text{H}})_4\text{Cl}]^+$ cation (Calcd. 1553.4180). ESI-MS experiments performed for **3(Me)** and **3(OMe)** reveal prominent ion peaks with m/z value = 1721.6028 and 1913.5325 respectively consistent with cationic $[\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-TPG}^{\text{Me}})_4\text{Cl}]^+$ and $[\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-TPG}^{\text{OMe}})_4\text{Cl}]^+$ complexes (Calcd. 1721.6058 for **3(Me)** and 1913.5448 for **3(OMe)**). The ESI-MS spectra of **3(H)**, **3(Me)** and **3(OMe)** are shown in Figs. 3–5.

DFT studies :

Despite several attempts, we were unable to grow the X-ray quality single crystals of the complexes of type **3(R)**. In an effort to get an insight into the ground state geometry, electronic structure and nature of frontier molecular orbitals (FMOs) of the complexes, the geometry optimization of all the three complexes were performed in gas phase without any ligand simplification with the

Fig. 3. ESI-mass spectrum (positive mode) of **3(H)**. Inset shows the expansion.

Fig. 4. ESI-mass spectrum (positive mode) of **3(Me)**. Inset shows the expansion.

Fig. 5. ESI-mass spectrum (positive mode) of 3(OMe). Inset shows the expansion.

$S = 0$ spin state. The optimized geometries of the complexes are shown in Fig. 6 and the significant metrical parameters are listed in Table 1. The optimized geometries of all the three complexes do not show significant differences in the coordination sphere around the rhenium centers which means that the TPG^R ligands bind in a similar fashion in the complexes. The complexes adopt a metal-metal bonded paddlewheel type structures, as shown in Fig. 6. The chlorine atom is bound axially to the Re1 atom, while the other axial position on Re2 is vacant. The Re1-Cl124 distance is ~ 2.42 Å. The Re1-Re2 bond distances in 3(R) (2.204–2.206 Å) are close to the other structurally characterized quadruply bonded Re₂⁶⁺ paddlewheel complexes¹⁵, indicating that presence or absence of one of the axial ligands has no appreciable effect on the Re–Re bond distance. The Re–N distances are longer for the Re atom that binds the axial chloride. The C–N bonds to the central carbon atoms (C17, C18, C19 and C20) of the planar CN₃ units of the TPG^R ligands show a delocalized bonding within the coordinated NCN unit [the C–N bond lengths lie in the range 1.351–1.367 Å]. The C–NH bond distance of ~ 1.38 Å is shorter than the C–N single bond distance indicating some C=N double

bond character, which enhances the basicity of the TPG^R ligands. The bite of the TPG^R ligands pulls the *trans* N–Re–N angles in to be less than 180° [the N–Re–N angles lie in the range 173.50–179.31°] and *cis* N–Re–N angles around Re fall in the range of 88–91°. The C_{phenyl} atoms are not coplanar with the guanidinate groups and the average length of the bonds made by the nitrogen atoms and the carbon atoms of the phenyl rings is 1.419 Å which means that there is no significant delocalization of the lone pair electron density from the N-atoms out onto the attached phenyl groups.

For one of the representative complexes 3(H), DFT calculation also shows that the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO, -7.3533 eV) corresponds to a δ interaction between the *d* orbitals of the rhenium atoms. The HOMO-1 and HOMO-2 are the π orbitals at *ca.* 0.65 eV lower in energy. The σ orbital is most stable and is found at HOMO-4 (-8.1697 eV). The σ and π orbitals also show some strong bonding interaction between the Cl atom and the rhenium center. The lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) is the metal based δ^* orbital at -4.8743 eV. The four highest occupied and three low-

Fig. 6. DFT-optimized molecular structures of $[3(R)]^+$. H atoms are omitted for clarity.

Table 1. Selected DFT optimized bond distances (Å) and angles (°) of $3(R)$ in the ground state

Bond parameter	$3(H)$	$3(Me)$	$3(OMe)$
Re1–Re2	2.206	2.206	2.204
Re1–Cl124	2.416	2.420	2.426
Re1–N3	2.130	2.130	2.132
Re1–N15	2.158	2.158	2.157
Re1–N7	2.129	2.130	2.127
Re1–N11	2.126	2.125	2.128
Re2–N4	2.096	2.096	2.095
Re2–N16	2.080	2.079	2.081
Re2–N8	2.091	2.090	2.091
Re2–N12	2.090	2.090	2.089
N3–Re1–N15	88.121	88.192	88.422
N3–Re1–N11	179.211	179.306	179.239

Table-1 (contd.)

N3–Re1–N7	89.958	89.938	89.905
N7–Re1–N11	90.565	90.475	90.333
N7–Re1–N15	177.895	177.926	178.145
N15–Re1–N11	91.347	91.386	91.330
Cl124–Re1–Re2	178.460	178.563	178.874
N4–Re2–N16	88.196	88.222	88.260
N16–Re2–N12	90.302	90.324	90.318
N12–Re2–N8	90.799	90.765	90.855
N8–Re2–N4	90.058	90.026	89.887
N4–Re2–N12	173.952	173.906	173.707
N16–Re2–N8	173.607	173.502	173.527

est unoccupied molecular orbitals of $3(H)$ are shown in Fig. 7. The HOMO-LUMO energy gap is 2.48 eV.

Fig. 7. Illustration of the 0.04 contour surface diagrams of the four highest occupied and three lowest unoccupied MOs calculated by DFT for **3(H)**.

Conclusion

The molten reactions of the quadruply bonded dirhenium synthon $[\text{Bu}_4\text{N}]_2\text{Re}_2\text{Cl}_8$ with different *para*-substituted triphenylguanidine ligands (HTPG^R) have been studied. This reaction is noteworthy because we have the first example of paddlewheel dirhenium(III) complexes, $[\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-TPG}^{\text{R}})_4\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$ with the HTPG^R ligands. The electrolytic nature of the complexes has been confirmed by conductivity measurements. The identities of the complexes have been established by different spectroscopic techniques (IR, NMR, UV-Vis and ESI-MS) and by the density functional theory calculations. DFT calculation for **3(H)** shows that HOMO corresponds to a δ interaction between the rhenium *d* orbitals whereas LUMO is the metal based δ^* orbital. Additional studies of the complexes remain to be pursued. One, obviously, is the synthesis and characterization of the one-electron oxidized product, $[\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-TPG}^{\text{R}})_4\text{Cl}]^{2+}$, with a Re_2^{7+} core. Attempts are now underway.

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